

International Associations and Internationalization of Higher Education (RUDN University case)

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Abstract. Membership in international organizations is crucial in the internationalization strategy of higher education institutions. It can help to enlarge the network, gain expertise from other organization and contribute in enhancing the visibility of an organization. Since its establishment in 1960, RUDN University has devoted great attention to participatin in international organizations. This process has been further enhanced since 2015, when RUDN University has joined the 5-100 University Excellence Program, promoted by the Russian Ministry of education. The authors analyses the benefits for RUDN University and the development of its international dimension thanks to its participation in international associations. The membership to IHF (Institut de Haute Formation aux Politiques Communautaires) has been chosen by the author as case study to demonstrate the benefits obtained by RUDN University from the membership.

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Value of internationalization

The internationalization of higher education has gained global dimension. Not only classical universities, but also international associations, as well as professional and business communities, often representatives of state bodies and civil society have become more actively involved in higher education.

Participation of Russian universities in international associations emphasizes the importance of the country as one of the global centers of education and science. To achieve this goal it is necessary to solve a number of problems.

First is the facilitation of information exchange. This is not about brain drain. The core of information exchange can be commercialization of the results of intellectual labor. The exchange of information involves the performance of scientists at international scientific conferences, seminars, workshops with reports on scientific developments, publication of articles in foreign scientific journals. Thus, it is possible to popularize developments among the international scientific community. International associations can serve as an institutional framework for such exchanges.

Secondly, international exchanges of scientists are, above all, mutual internships of young researchers in scientific institutions, carried out on the basis of intergovernmental, inter-university agreements. When organizing joint case studies, their results can be the fruit of common labor, and this will become the basis for strengthening inter-country cooperation and provide access to other areas of interaction (primarily in economic field).

Thirdly, presentation of the results of intellectual activity abroad. This task is important from the point of raising of the ranking of a particular institution of higher education, in which

development has appeared. This task can become a logical continuation of the first task - information exchange in the scientific and educational spheres.

To form good national policy in the field of science and education, it is necessary to understand world development trends in these areas. For example, it is necessary to intensify the cooperation of Russian universities with European ones. Favorable conditions have been created for this. The most successful example of this kind of cooperation today are grants under the EU Erasmus+ program. The program provides an opportunity in collaboration with top universities abroad to improve their own ranking. Another example is the implementation of the Horizon 2020 program, which meets the objectives of the innovative development of the economies.

The modern world is faced with a large number of global problems, the solution of which requires the combined efforts of many states. It seems that such problems are more easily solved within the framework of international organizations, which, thanks to their institutional nature, establish clear frameworks and standards for the development of solutions generally accepted. These solutions can later be successfully adapted to the national reality, being a product and at the same time a resource for “internal use”.

RUDN University as a member of international associations

RUDN University's participation in the framework of international educational associations is regulated by the local Decree of the University under signature of the Rector [1].

The first international educational association which RUDN University joined as an institutional member had been the International Association of Universities - one of the most influential and largest associations uniting universities around the world. This happened in 1965.

The second wave of getting membership in international associations comes in the 90-s of the XX century. It was caused by international developments in the world as a result of the collapse of the USSR and the emergence of new states in the post-Soviet space. Then an important task for Russia was to maintain positions and roles in the scientific and educational spheres among neighbors – in the Commonwealth of Independent States region. In 1993 RUDN University became an institutional member of the Eurasian Universities Association. This association was aimed at preserving the values and traditions in education and science accumulated over the years of existence of a single multinational state - the Soviet Union, and solving problems in the humanitarian and technical spheres in the Eurasian space.

The third wave of gaining membership in international associations related to 2016-2018. During this period RUDN University was gaining momentum as a part of the Russian educational project “5-100”. This project has been aimed at improving positions of international educational rankings designed until 2020 [2]. RUDN University was directed to solving problems of international recognition and acquiring the status of one of the most internationalized universities in the world. During this period in accordance with the concept proposed in the “Roadmap” of the “5-100” project RUDN University became an institutional member of 15 international educational associations. As of June 2019 RUDN University was an institutional member of 41 international educational associations within which the university provides multi-format collaboration covering both educational and scientific fields [3]. As of June 2020 the number of international educational associations with RUDN's membership has increased up to 48.

All international educational associations can be divided into three categories: general international educational associations, professional associations with coordination of RUDN University on behalf of separate educational divisions, network universities. International educational associations of general character, as a rule, do not have a strictly defined orientation in areas of university education. They include classical universities with a variety of training profiles, research institutes and centers. The objectives of such organizations include cooperation between member universities over the widest range of educational and scientific issues.

Professional associations are characterized by a strict focus on certain areas of education – medical, economic, engineering, IT-technologies, environmental, etc. The interaction between universities in such organizations is aimed at strengthening professional ties. Such organizations

include both specialized HEIs, and classical multi-profile universities. The participation of the universities in professional associations is coordinated by separate educational divisions and professors individually.

Network universities, as a rule, are represented by consortia comprising various universities from several countries. Organizationally such consortia are more decentralized. Their universities participate in networks on a voluntary basis, but in compliance with the network's charter, membership fees are not mandatory. A particular feature of the network universities is that they only provide the institutional membership of HEIs. At the same time network universities can have both multi-profile and strictly professional orientation.

As of June 2020 RUDN University is an institutional member of 48 international educational associations, among them 16 associations can be categorized as general international educational associations, 28 organizations can be classified as *professional associations*, and the category of *network universities* includes 4 organizations:

- CIS (Commonwealth of Independent States) Network University
- SCO (Shanghai Cooperation Organization) Network University
- BRICS (Brazil, Russia, India, China, South Africa) Network University
- French-Russian University.

To reach the tasks leading to the strategic goal of international recognition of the university, and implementation of functions of an internationally recognized university, it is necessary to promote participation in the framework of international educational organizations with institutional membership of a HEI. In this regard educational units of a university has an important role. They provide membership in general international and professional associations in accordance with the profiles and specialties within their framework.

Along with the quantitative side it is necessary to take into account the qualitative side of the issue. It is not enough to be a member of as many international educational organizations as possible; it is necessary to carry out joint work with each specific organization. That will have final effect not only inside educational departments, but also at the university as a whole.

From this point of view, the development of criteria for the effectiveness of participation of RUDN University in international associations is considered to be rational. In this case the criteria, which are quantitative in nature, reveal the qualitative side of the question:

- new developed curricula with partner universities-members of international organizations;
- signed agreements over implementation of double degree programs with partner universities-members of international organizations;
- signed agreements on the implementation of internships and exchange programs with partner universities that are members of international organizations;
- number of students arriving at RUDN University from partner universities that are members of international organizations in the framework of signed agreements;
- number of professors arrived at RUDN University for lecturing from partner universities that are members of international organizations;
- number of professors of RUDN University sent for lecturing to partner university-members of international organizations;
- number of joint scientific publications of professors of RUDN University and partner university-members of international organizations, cited in international databases (Scopus, WoS, etc.);
- number of publications of RUDN University professors in international publications of partner university-members of international organizations;
- number of experts from the academic community and employers voting for RUDN University in international rankings;
- organization of summer / winter schools on a joint basis, as well as practice bases for undergraduate and graduate students;

- participation of RUDN University and partner university-members of international organizations in the implementation of consortium projects (like Capacity Building in the framework of the Erasmus+ program);
- mutual recognition of the curricula of the RUDN University and partner university-members of international organizations.

RUDN University is a member of IHF

IHF (Institut de Haute Formation aux Politiques Communautaires) is a non-profit association of practitioners and volunteers established in Brussels in 2003 with the mission of increasing awareness on the European Union and function as a platform for exchange among practitioners from civil society, academia, public sector and industry on the many facets of European integration [4].

IHF specializes in research projects and assists RUDN University in the development and implementation of international research projects (in particular, Horizon-2020). IHF has provided consulting support in the design of a project proposal under the Horizon-2020 program. Project's title "Understanding Migration Mobility Models: Developing Scenarios for Medium and Long-Term Migration" ID: MIGRATION-01-2019. Name of the project proposal: "EU migration mobility models and social stability: development of scenarios for medium-term and long-term migration" (academic coordinator of the project is Associate Professor of the Department of Marketing at the Faculty of Economics of RUDN University E.A. Degtereva).

Benefits of membership at IHF

- increasing the level of internationalization, assisting RUDN University in international activities at wide European educational sites by increasing contacts with institutional members of the organization (universities, international educational organizations);
- increasing the visibility of RUDN University in the international sphere - organizing the participation of RUDN University in international forums, meetings, conferences;
- privileged status of RUDN University in the financing of international educational projects (IHF mediates the distribution of educational projects grants - internships, trainings, student exchanges, joint researches);
- organization international trainings for students and staff of RUDN University on the basis of IHF;
- possibility of free use of the premises of the IHF headquarters in Brussels, located close to the main structures of the EU (European Commission, Council of Europe, European Parliament), for organizing conferences, status cultural and educational events of RUDN University.
- possibility of cooperation with universities with high positions in international rankings.
- increasing projects under the Erasmus program and, through this, increasing the number of partner universities for the implementation of international student mobility programs;
- replenishing the research base on European education, security, migration, sociological issues through access to IHF resources;
- RUDN University specialists who have been trained at the IHF.

Globalization, international associations and internationalization of higher education

Since the beginning of the 21st century the main trend of the world development has been globalization, which embraced all countries and regions of the planet. According to some researchers, globalization is a qualitatively new stage in the internationalization of all aspects of industrial and social activity. This process is manifested in the formation of the world economic system, which includes financial, market and communication network, and also determines social development in the whole [5, p. 6].

At the same time globalization is the main driver of internationalization of higher education [6, p. 2]. Globalization creates the space for HEIs' interaction in educational and scientific fields.

For today besides interaction the processes of competition between universities have been observed. This phenomenon is very clearly seen on the level of world educational rankings.

At the same time over the past decades tendencies opposite to globalization began to appear in the world. International society realized that not all the problems can be solved by globalization. Tendencies of so called “glocalization” (globalization at the local level) and regionalization were starting to rise in many regions of the world [7, p. 33-34]. This has also affected the higher education sector. It became clear that some problems can be effectively addressed at the regional level. Societies considered that instead of being in a competition, universities, on the contrary, should work together to achieve global goals. It was for this purpose that universities alliances began to appear from the end of the 20th century in international educational area. One such an example is the Coimbra Group.

Founded in 1985 and formally constituted by Charter in 1987, the Coimbra Group is an association of long-established European multidisciplinary universities of high international standard. The Coimbra Group is committed to creating special academic and cultural ties in order to promote, for the benefit of its members, internationalisation, academic collaboration, excellence in learning and research, and service to society. It is also the purpose of the Group to influence European educational policy and to develop best practice through mutual exchange of experience [8].

The other opportunity to develop joint potential is to create network universities in the regional framework. As an example it is the CIS (Commonwealth of Independent States) Network University, which was initiated by RUDN University in 2008. By the way RUDN University became the headquarters of it. On June 11, 2009, in Moscow, an Agreement on the Consortium to establish the CIS Network University was signed.

The main goals of creating of this kind of university Consortium in post-Soviet space were:

- development of a common educational space of the member states' universities on the post-Soviet area through implementation of joint educational programs, organization of students' exchanges, new forms of interuniversity cooperation;

- creation of mechanisms for development of academic mobility of students and professors within the framework of the CIS;

- support of intercultural dialogue in the student environment, preservation, development and mutual enrichment of culture, languages, historical and national traditions of the peoples of the member states of the CIS [9]. The Consortium includes 38 leading universities from 9 CIS member states.

CIS Network University was created in the image of the Erasmus Mundus European Program – an integrated international educational program jointly implemented by an international consortium of universities. As Mario De Martino, a researcher of European educational programmes mentions in his work, that CIS Network University as well as SCO (Shanghai Cooperation Organization) Network University are two educational programmes inspired to Erasmus Mundus, aimed at strengthening the academic mobility of Russia with former Soviet countries and China [10].

External Internationalization and Internationalization-at-home

International educational organizations can provide an institutional framework for fruitful cooperation between universities.

Internationalization of higher education has become an integral part of the globalization processes. Internationalization can be viewed as a strategy of society and universities, which they apply in response to the numerous requirements for universities in the context of globalization, as well as a tool of higher education for preparing specialists for involvement in the global world. In general, internationalization is perceived as a necessary process of including an international, intercultural or global aspect in the goals, functions, and implementation of higher education programs. At the same time, experts define 2 types of internationalization: external and internal (at-home). According to the American researcher Ph. Altbach, external internationalization

implies the promotion of the university and its key figures in the international community. The main examples are sending students to study abroad, setting up a university branch abroad, or participation in interuniversity partnerships. Internal internationalization consists of strategies and approaches designed to apply international experience in a local university setting, for example, by incorporating a global and comparative perspective into educational programs or by attracting foreign students, academics and educators [11, p. 76].

The experts of the International Association of Universities understand internal internationalization as, first of all, the internationalization of curricula. They propose 2 ways to achieve internal internationalization: first, to guide students towards professional prospects outside the country of study. Secondly, to carry out professional development of faculties, increasing their ability to integrate international / intercultural aspects in teaching. Both paths are aimed at the internationalization of curricula [12, p. 33].

Based on these provisions, it can be stated that RUDN University, as one of the most internationally oriented and multicultural universities in the world, has all the necessary basis for the development of internal internationalization.

Participation of universities in international associations is an imperative of modernity and a new trend in the development of international educational activities. This trend has very many modifications. Taking high positions in international educational rankings directly depends on participation of the university in international prestigious educational organizations

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